

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

AWARENESS AND EXTENT OF USAGE OF E-BOOKS IN UNIVERSITY LIBRARIES

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ANNOTATION: The article assessed usage of Electronic books in Delta State University, Abraka and Novena University, Ogume, Nigeria. Undergraduate students were randomly selected for the study. The population of the study was 253 300 and 400 level students of the institutions studied. The instrument employed for data collection was the questionnaire. The 253 students were administered the research tool but 231 of them were retrieved and used for the investigation. The collected data were examined using the frequency count and percentage. The study concluded that the respondents use the e-books to a very high extent; in terms of frequency of usage, the study concluded that on the average, utilization of e-books by the students was weekly; the greatest challenges to e-book provision and usage were insufficient e-books in the library and power supply in that order. Therefore, aggressive e-book collection development is here suggested. Academic Libraries should make e-books readily available and easily reached so as to encourage more, the use of the resources.

Keyword: E-book, E-book usage, Extent of usage, E-book awareness, University libraries, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

E-books are books that are in electronic form. It may well be explained as the electronic adaptation of a printed book. An e-Book could basically be depicted as electronic book. E-books may be books initially published in a long-established way but digitized for use as an e-book or born digital [1]. E-books are normally intended for consultation on dedicated e-book readers, but, almost any sophisticated electronic gadget that have a adjustable viewing screen, such as computers (laptop, desktop, as well as other microcomputer appliances), tablet computers and Smartphone can also be deployed to explore e-books.

Theoretically, e-books are books in digital form, though there is big disparity. Both of them are in electronic format but they vary. Despite the fact that e-books appear in internet websites which enhances its wider usage and coverage, digital books on the other hand are limited to a particular library and with restricted users. Nevertheless, digital books can become e- books whenever they are positioned on the institutional portals/ website blog and made available through the internet connectivity to such portals to the public [1].

Presently in Nigeria, electronic books are gradually representing an increasingly important component of the resource collection of academic libraries even though in the last few years the emergence and integration of e-books have been at a slow pace. The acquisition of e-books is an

obvious accreditation necessity for libraries as directed by the National Universities Commission (NUC). This may well be associated to the reality that e-books are yet to be recognized as a way out of the paucity of textbooks in tertiary stage of teaching and learning in Nigeria [2].

A good number of libraries will continue to simultaneously offer both digital and print collections for years to come even though libraries of various types are embracing digital collections. Acquisition of new journals, abstracting as well as indexing services and magazines are greatly in the direction of digital, while e-books are in their infant stage in terms of presence in the collection of libraries. Digital collections are preferred for a good number of reasons. These include the following:

- e-books can be associated/accessed from and to abstracting and indexing.
- access can be gotten even from the comfort of patron's office, home, or dormitory even without visiting the physical library.
- the library can get usage statistics that are not available for print collections; and
- space is no challenge in e-book collections environment, and they are comparatively very easy to preserve. In fact, if the entire space costs and processing costs are considered, e-book collections may as well result in total reductions in library financing [3].

Over the years, a good number of libraries have started offering e-books to their esteemed

patrons [4]. The electronic e-books provided to users are usually digital types of books which also are in print. E-books have the same substance as the print version save for the fact that they are created in a different layout/format. These collections of resources offer some advantages as against their print counterpart to both the library and the patrons. To the patrons, they offer unhindered accessibility, they are accessible outside the physical library, copying text and images pasting, and full-text searching. The advantage e-books offer to the library is that they don't require shelving/ re-shelving, shelf space and cannot be mutilated, lost, or stolen.

The circulation component of the library is the front end and a strategic link between the library and the patrons. The inputs from the acquisition, reference, cataloging and classification divisions and bindery are raw materials that the circulation unit uses to provide services to patrons. Earnestly, the circulation unit is the front end for all users and it is the duty of the circulation librarian as a foremost player in the scheme of things is to be acquainted with patrons' needs/requirement in the library. As the foremost player, the Circulation Librarian join's patrons' needs together with the library holdings through Selective Dissemination of Information (SDI) [4].

Also, the circulation unit of the library is responsible for checking materials in and out, whether in electronic format or in print. As it concerns e-books. However, that responsibility can come to fruition only if the entire system is computerized/ automated. The introduction of automation to library service delivery has brought about the need for information professionals to enhance information provision services to the teeming users.

Academic libraries are primary segment of the higher education institutions. Therefore, Librarians must if they still desire to be relevant not be told to brace up and confront the evolving Information Communication Technology. Effective and efficient use of e-books by users is in vogue, not just acquiring without effective use. Before now, circulation information were gathered/ collected manually using the circulation history in the "book card/date tag" from books. However, with the coming of automation systems in libraries, information gathering has been greatly simplified. [5] acknowledged that

circulation analyses seems to be one amongst traditional methods employed in collection evaluation as well as use studies in libraries. The information gathered from circulation analyses have been used in areas such as guiding management decisions in allocating physical space for materials, evaluating collection development policies; identifying information resources that are for offsite storage, funds allocation for materials; in addition to suggesting methods of de-selection. In fact, frequent circulation evaluation of materials in a library collection is an indicator of that library's effectiveness; which invariably means that the collection is serving its purpose.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Inadequate awareness has been acknowledged as a setback within the past few years due to the realization that the methods that have been used overtime for assessing usage; loan statistics and similar measures did not bring to the fore accurate/adequate information about the real pattern of usage [6].

[7] noted that the assessment of the extent of awareness and use of e-books has been neglected and research regarding e-books had been concentrated on technologies assessment in terms of vendor prerequisite. Also, how e-book users perceive it as well as the reasons behind eBook use or non-use are significant elements for libraries and e-book publishers, but awareness and usage seems neglected.

Therefore, an examination of the issues of awareness, adoption and usage of e-books in libraries is needed in other to find out what the challenges are and to make certain the incorporation of eBooks in library collections. The moment practical challenges of eBook awareness and adoption are identified, the subject whether users are aware and involved in using e-books become pertinent.

Objectives of the Study

The principal aim of this research is to investigate the extent/degree of awareness and usage of e-books in academic libraries. The objectives are:

- (1). To investigate the extent of awareness of e-books in the academic libraries studied.
- (2). To ascertain the extent of e-books usage in the academic libraries.
- (3). To determine frequency/regularity of eBooks usage by users.

(4). To ascertain the challenges of e-book usage.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Past literature has revealed that investigation with reference to e-books has concentrated to a great extent on the appraisal of technology instead of on how patrons perceive e-books as well as the basic factors underlying usage. There are good number factors that might influence use, for example, the screen size of the reading gadget, may have an effect on reading ease as well as understanding [8]. In addition, a large amount of acquisition funds are being used up by university libraries in Nigeria on Electronic Books (e-books) or on implementation of e-books platforms [9]; [10]. Therefore, it is strategically vital to discern whether the funds spent on the libraries including the effort put into making e-books available is effective. In fact, how the e-book resources are being used and users' awareness of e-books are vital variables for collection management and collection building [11]; [12].

Researchers understand and embark upon the assessment of e-book usage in diverse ways and relative to their institutions, resulting to variety of opinions in literature and research. As preference and interest for e-books increase it should be noted that university libraries have been in the forefront regarding e-books and reference materials provision for their users. Together with printed books, e-books exist to serve the needs of library users [13].

[5] noted that circulation statistics supplied by vendors don't show e-books that are in use, do not make available information concerning the reasons for use, user satisfaction with the format and how e-books are perceived. As a result, there has arisen interest in the study of e-book usage and in-depth user satisfaction. For example, [14] submitted that 59.6 percent of the subjects studied mostly use printed information resources, but occasionally use e-books. The investigation revealed further that hardcopy information resources are very relevant even with the emergence of e-books.

Also, Georgas [15] investigation discovered that e-book usage was low, and as a result needed more promotion to increase awareness. The scholar emphasized further that patrons' interest with respect to e-book usage was very close to nothing. [16] in addition, conducted a study in

eleven Africa countries (Nigeria inclusive), and the scholars revealed that e-books were found in 14 libraries (67%), but not existing in 7 libraries (33%). The investigation as a consequence concluded that e-books are thus far readily available in some but not all academic establishments in Africa.

[17] examined e-book usage at the University of Liverpool and reported that all subject domains had been well used (mathematics not included), and that the number of titles not used is gradually reducing each year; that older e-books appeal more and is continually attracting considerable usage.

[1] in his research noted that in an investigation done by a few American scholars (July 2014), it was revealed that e-books appreciation has improved tremendously in the US. This improvement in 2014 was because 28% of adults did use e-book, as against 23% in 2013. Also, this increment was attained because 50% of the subjects studied as at 2014 did had a dedicated gadget (a tablet or an e-reader, as against 30% with a gadget in 2013. In Nigeria, the precise number of e-books understanding populace is yet to be established but the number may be low even amongst scholars. The explanation for this lapse could vary from soaring poverty as well as high illiteracy in our nation to inadequate knowledge of e-books devices amongst the entire public. Resulting from the above lapses, [18] acknowledged that considering the question of e-book usage is a continuous exercise and additional studies are needed.

In addition, [19] in a London University College study of a group of students, reported that e-books usage was enhanced due to the lapses with the print resources collection, particularly in the sciences and engineering disciplines. The result showed that the clientele were still more willing to use the print collection resources, and would gladly do so when given the required resources. Additionally, [20] noted that in the case for non-reference and reference collections, e-books were utilized more when compared to the hardcopy of those particular editions.

Four studies were done at the University of Rochester, California State University Libraries, University of Pittsburgh, in addition to Wayne State University with data gotten from net Library e-books. In all, Gibbons reported that of the 10 net Library e-book collections available to

University of Rochester users, only one is in print and is owned by the university.

CHALLENGES TO E-BOOK USAGE

Electronic books can be navigated and search easily than their printed counterpart. This factor makes them more favored by student and researchers. Equally, e-books allow libraries to service remote users- it is particularly helpful for university libraries in institutions that are into distance learning programs. E-books solve a number of challenges in libraries [21]. E-books don't get damaged or wear out, can't easily get lost and don't need physical storage space. A shortcoming of e-books usage, and in actual fact one of the variables that have slow down e-book adoption in the book trade, is the embarrassment number of commonly unsuited formats in addition to the unfriendly Digital Rights Management (DRM) schemes.

The coming of e-books and their incorporation into library collections, although have provided opportunities for librarians, they have equally generated a range of challenges [22]; [23]; [24]; [25]. This is due to the fact that unlike physical books, e-book's purchase, organization, as well as access are at variance

from the hard copy books. Also Issues associated with technicality, dependability and functionality, are very important for libraries desiring to create e-book collection/platform. Issues such as hardware/software compatibility and capability, maintenance, storage, search / retrieval functionality, interface usability are likely challenges libraries will encounter when administering e-books physically.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology used was survey technique. The population of the study was 253 300 and 400 level students of the institutions studied. The research tool employed for the investigation was the questionnaire, which was structured to determine relevant information about e- books usage in the university libraries studied. The research tool was validated through the use of 2 experts in the field. Undergraduate students were randomly selected for the study. The 253 students were administered the research tool but 231 of them were retrieved and used for the investigation. Selecting both universities was anchored on the premise that the universities were automated. The collected data were examined using frequency count and simple percentage..

RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Table 1

Distribution of respondents by institution

Delta State University, Abraka.	146 (63.2%)
Novena University, Ogume	85 (36.8%)
Total	231

Table 1 indicates that 85 (36.8%) students from Novena University participated in the study, while 146 (63.2%) were from the Delta State

University. This result shows that more of Delta State University students were used in the study.

Table 2

Extent of Awareness of E-books in the library

Items	No. of Respondents	%
High Extent	198	85.7
Low Extent	20	8.7
Undecided cases	13	5.6
Total	231	100

On extent of e-books awareness in the university libraries, the analysis in Table 2 shows that the students were very much aware to a high extent of the availability of Electronic books. Out of 231 respondents administered the

questionnaire, 198 (85.7 %) affirmed that they were aware to a high extent of e-books existence in the libraries, whereas 20 (8.7%) reported that they were not aware, with 13 (5.6 %) undecided cases.

Table 3

The Extent of E-book usage in the library

Items	No. of Respondents	%
Very High Extent	85	36.8
High Extent	52	22.5

Undecided cases	37	16.0
Low Extent	30	13.0
Very Low Extent	27	11.7
Total	231	100

Also, on the extent of e-books usage in the library, the study found that 85 (36.8 %) of the students acknowledged that they use e-books in the Library to a very high extent, whereas 52 (22.5%) noted that they use e-books to a high

extent. 37 (16.0%) undecided cases were recorded. 30(13.0%) and 27(11.7%) respectively were for low extent and very low extent. The study concluded that the respondents use the e-books to a very high extent.

Table 4

Frequency of E-books usage in the library

Items	No. of Respondents	%
I uses e-books daily	63	27.3
Weekly	72	31.2
Monthly	34	14.7
I don't make use of e-books	62	26.8
Total	231	100

On how often do the respondents use e-books, the research showed in Table 4 that 63 (27.3%) of them uses e-books daily, while 72 (31.2%) use e-books weekly. Also, 34 (14.7%) of

the respondents use e-books monthly, even as 62(28.8%) of them don't make use of e-books. The study concluded that on the average, utilization of e-books by the students is weekly.

Table 5

Challenges of using e-books

Items	No. of Respondents	%
Power supply	61	26.4
Slow bandwidth	22	9.5
Inadequate e-books in the library	96	41.6
Technical issues	25	10.8
Inadequate knowledge of the use of the e-book platform in the library	27	11.7
Total	231	100

Table 4 showed that 96 (41.6%) of respondents affirmed that inadequate e-books in the library was their greatest challenge, while 61(26.4%) said it was power supply. The least challenge in the distribution was slow bandwidth, 22 (9.5%). Therefore it was concluded that the greatest challenges were inadequate e-books in the library and power supply in that order.

DISCUSSIONS

The students were very much aware to a high extent of the availability of electronic books in the libraries. This finding did not agree with [6] who reported that inadequate awareness has been acknowledged as a setback within the past few years due to the realization that the methods employed have been used overtime without success. Plus or minus, the library has a strong

role to play to ensure creating awareness regarding availability of electronic-books in the library. [26]. They found that e-book awareness and extent of e-book usage amongst the students was low. In that investigation, 57% respondents were not aware of the availability of e-books, while 60% of them have not made use of an e-book. This perhaps affected negatively the extent of usage that study.

In terms of frequency of usage, the study concluded that on the average, utilization of e-books by the students was weekly. This is above average. This finding did not agree with [26]; their research revealed that despite the accessibility to a wide range of e-resources (including e-books) their use rate was low.

A number of studies that dwelt on e-book usage found that even with increased awareness regarding the e-resource universally, it has been noticed that rate of use together with usage pattern in a number of educational libraries in African countries and Nigeria in particular appear very limited [27]. Despite the fact that a number of avid library patrons report that they visit library branches less but use the library website often for e-book downloads, the use of its print counterpart is more compared to e-books.

In a study of e-book usage and opinion at the University of Liverpool, it was reported by [28] that e-books were made use of primarily for schoolwork and for research inquiries. Undergraduate students exploit e-books also for study (80 %) as well as for research (71 %). That is, the students use e-books frequently. However, Faculty members to some extent have dissimilar usage routine, accessing e-books in smaller amount but frequently for learning purposes (31 %) but more frequently for research (85 %). Also, [29] researched on the frequency of e-resources use and found that the frequency of e-resources utilization including e-books was extremely low.

The greatest challenges to e-book provision and usage were inadequate e-books in the library and power supply in that order. This finding corroborates [24] who acknowledged that issues such as hardware/software compatibility and capability, maintenance, adequacy, storage, search / retrieval functionality, power supply [30], interface usability are likely challenges libraries will encounter when administering e-books.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concluded that the respondents use the e-books to a very high extent; in terms of frequency of usage, the study concluded that on the average, utilization of e-books by the students was weekly; the greatest challenges to e-book provision and usage were insufficient e-books in the library and power supply in that order.

E-books are yet to be fully integrated into some libraries in Nigeria. However, the introduction of e-books in the university libraries studied has made substantial input compared to their print equivalent. Students are responsive to suggestions regarding particular resources by their friends, teachers, or a librarian. Therefore, educating both staff and students on how to appraise Web resources along with search tactics are imperative. In fact, awareness advocacy is highly required to enhance further usage. Ease of use remains the sole most important issue for information use. Library users prefer e-books only if the e-books make their learning and research easier, and their information needs assuaged. The speed of access, desktop/laptop access as well as the skill to download, print out the downloaded information in addition to knowing how to send research articles are factors that make use of e-books possible.

Therefore, aggressive e-book collection development is here suggested. Academic Libraries should make e-books readily available and easily reached so as to encourage more, the use of the resources.

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